

STUDENT INVOLVEMENT IN SOUND AND MUSIC COMPUTING RESEARCH: CURRENT PRACTICES AT KTH AND KMH

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ABSTRACT

To engage students in and beyond course activities has been a working practice both at KTH Sound and Music Computing group and at KMH Royal College of Music since many years. This paper collects experiences of involving students in research conducted within the two institutions.

We describe how students attending our courses are given the possibility to be involved in our research activities, and we argue that their involvement both contributes to develop new research and benefits the students in the short and long term. Among the assignments, activities, and tasks we offer in our education programs are pilot experiments, prototype development, public exhibitions, performing, composing, data collection, analysis challenges, and bachelor and master thesis projects that lead to academic publications.

1. INTRODUCTION

At both KTH Royal Institute of technology and KMH Royal College of Music we conduct teaching and research in Sound and Music Computing, and to engage students in research tasks is at the centre of the offered learning activities. Undergraduate research participation has been a pedagogical practice at KTH since many years back, and similarly, with the recent increase in artistic-based research at KMH, the foundation for constructively engaging students of music in research is well established. In this paper we aim to argue for why this is a practice that benefits both under- and postgraduate students as well as faculty members, and how we plan to continue developing our pedagogical approach.

There are well-documented benefits of including undergraduate students in research, both for enhancing research skills [1], general study skills [2], and building a community [3]. Thus, we know that students' participation in research activities is rewarding. Many of our courses

have project work components, and the description and instructions which set the framework for these are typically inspired by how research projects are normally carried out. Roberts and Allen [4] measured research participation cost-benefit ratio along seven items, and they found that the students' perceived educational value of research participation was higher than the drawbacks or costs they experienced in research participation. The most prominent factor was that this participation complements teaching, while the expected influence on own future research was lower.

Several research tasks can be expensive in terms of workload, for instance data collection in listening experiments, and students can often take on such tasks efficiently and with a positive effect on learning. However, many studies show the potential risks of student research involvement. Considering that a major driver for the student is that research experience complements teaching, it has been argued [5] that the ambiguous role of the teacher/researcher can confuse the student with regards to divergent interests in learning and in researching.

To let students carry out a faculty researcher's study can potentially lead to ethical problems: First, there are few standards or guidelines for involving students to do research, and even participate as research subjects [6]. Second, the power differential between faculty and students makes students a vulnerable population and research activities should not be placed on them just because of them being easily accessible [7]. Also, power inequities are known to cause the stronger to act in the best interest of the weaker, which can harm the trust relationship and thus the quality of the work [8]. A more tenable approach may be to encourage and allow students to formulate and conduct research with a higher degree of independence. Still, senior researchers have the important role of warning students to avoid common pitfalls, given the short time available for many of the projects.

It is quite common that postgraduates supervise undergraduates, and a study on research-based teaching activities presents five tensions between faculty, postgraduate and undergraduate students [9]. Of particular interest is that while undergraduates can increase research productiv-

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ity, they also require more time for training, and postgraduates vary in their mentoring abilities. Furthermore, the undergraduate and postgraduate relationship was found to generate hierarchical structures that may have a negative effect on their work environment. As such, postgraduates' involvement should be considered carefully.

Even if undergraduates need more time for mentoring and training, they are an important asset. To attract students to participate and engage in research activities, we need to advertise their involvement: lack of visibility has been identified as a barrier to student participation, both in terms of awareness of ongoing research, and of results dissemination [10]. As incentive to motivate students to participate to research projects with both advise and assist students in submitting their works for publication and presentation in international conferences, such as the SMC conference, the Nordic SMC Conference and SMC Sweden. ¹.

Interestingly, teachers with larger course loads are slightly more likely to engage in undergraduate research than their colleagues [11]. This contrasts the above mentioned potential problems and risks and indicates that even for faculty, the benefits of having students active in research are greater than the perceived costs.

In the following, we describe the backgrounds of KTH and KMH in terms of teaching and researching in sound and music computing, and we provide some examples of current and recent undergraduate work.

2. BACKGROUND

In 2016, an agreement between KTH and KMH was signed that declared the intention to intensify collaboration in both research and education. Since then, external funding was obtained to develop a framework for master level work, including thesis, in the wider area of music technology, which aims at the conduction projects in collaboration with companies and organisations involving students from both KTH and KMH. Recently (June 2019), the research centre NAVET² was established, with the aim of exploring new research direction in the intersectional area Art, Technology and Design. This research centre involves currently four of the main higher education institutions in Stockholm, among them KTH and KMH. This dense network of established collaboration creates the environment to further develop strategies to combine research and education at KMH and KTH.

The Sound and Music Computing research group at KTH originates from the Speech, Music and Hearing lab. The Music Acoustics group, led by Johan Sundberg, started early to publish master theses in the Quarterly Progress and Status Report series, for instance by Erik Jansson in 1966.³ This started a long tradition within the field of SMC at KTH, currently lead by the SMC group⁴, characterized by an ongoing exchange of research activity between undergraduate students and faculty.

¹ <http://smcsweden.se/>

² <https://www.kth.se/navet>

³ https://www.speech.kth.se/qpsr/show_by_author.php?author=Jansson%2C+E.

⁴ <https://www.kth.se/mid/research/smc>

At KMH, research has become an increasingly important part of the faculty and students' activities. This was further emphasised by the move into the new campus in 2016, where an advanced digital infrastructure and a concert hall with a loudspeaker dome with up to 45 speakers were built with music research in mind. Today, research at KMH is conducted in a variety of music-related subjects such as artistic research, music education, music and health and music technology.

The joint organization of the conference *Music and Music Science* conference in 2004⁵, chaired by Johan Sundberg and Bill Brunson, made it clear that KTH and KMH had to collaborate in both research and teaching. In the current close collaboration between KMH and KTH, in particular with four KMH teachers also enrolled at KTH as doctoral students, we have activities across the institutions. These four teachers cover the topics of music production, jazz and folk music performance, as well as composition. Their simultaneous affiliation as researchers and teachers enables them to integrate projects of their research into the teaching practice at KMH. This way, students are introduced within their artistic education to research practice in SMC, which diminishes observed or foreseeable barriers between the different research and academic traditions.

3. ACTIVITIES

In the following we present a selection of examples from courses, degree projects, exhibitions, and research projects where undergraduate students are involved with research. Typically, the results are disseminated publicly—either as presentations, publications, concerts, or exhibitions.

3.1 Course activities at KTH

In the framework of the *DT2213 Musical Communication and Music Technology* course (7.5 ECTS, second cycle), students work in a small project as one part of the course. In previous years, this study was suggested and designed by the students, but since 2019 all students get the same research challenge and are divided into groups based on competence matching. Course evaluations confirm that the new approach is more appreciated. To increase motivation, the study is set in a realistic environment and is disseminated through a public presentation, currently held at the Swedish Museum of Performing Arts.⁶ In this way, the students can collectively contribute to ongoing research.

In spring 2019 a new bachelor course *DM1579/2579 Media Production* (6 ECTS first cycle/7.5 ECTS, second cycle) was developed at KTH. The main project work for this course, to be carried out in teams, is the development, production and postproduction of an interactive documentary [12]. Interactive documentaries are a new form of non-fiction narrative that uses at its core action, choice, and immersion to create storytelling. Through this project the students are challenged to engage with the most current

⁵ http://www.speech.kth.se/music/music_and_music_science_2004.pdf

⁶ <https://scenkonstmuseet.se/>

issues in media and sound production (non-linear storytelling, audience interaction, and object-based media). Although only one cohort so far has taken this new course, it is clear that some of these students productions will contribute to research in media and sound production. Additionally, through this course bachelor students come into contact with research as often they choose to select a research topic or a research team as the subject of their production.

Further examples of second-cycle courses that provide students with the possibilities to conduct research projects as part of the course examination are *DT2300 Sound in Interaction*, *DM2350 Human Perception for Information Technology*, and *DT2470 Music Informatics* (all 7.5 ECTS, second cycle). In all these cases, students are provided with a list of project proposals to choose from, which they then develop, supported by faculty staff, by shaping a detailed project plan, implementing this plan, and documenting the outcome in form of public project presentations that resemble settings of scientific conferences. In the current version of the *DT2300 Sound in Interaction* course, students work on a theme; for example for 2020 the theme is *The soundscape of the future*, connected to one of the current research projects run by the SMC group at KTH. In this and other courses students can work with technology such as permanent installations [13], sensor technology (i.e. motion capture systems), 3D printing, and laser cutting.

In the *DT2215/DT2216 Advanced Individual Course in Music Communication* courses (6.0 and 9.0 ECTS, second cycle) students can work on individual research projects assigned by researchers and that are usually associated to ongoing research projects. Often this research results in international publications (see for example [14, 15]).

In *DM2799 Advanced Project Course in Media Technology* (7.5 ECTS, second cycle), student groups choose and work on a project suggested and supervised by faculty researchers and teachers. With this approach, faculty have an outspoken interest in proposing good projects as they lead to results relevant for research and possibly attracting further engagement in Master's theses.

In summary, the above mentioned courses create a large diversity of research areas in which the students are stimulated to integrate their learning process with scientifically novel research projects. These areas comprise among other, the design of new music instruments and interfaces, sonification, music perception, expressive body motion, music performance, and music information retrieval. With this background, students come well prepared to do a rewarding master thesis work.

3.2 Course activities at KMH

A large part of the research conducted by doctoral students enrolled in the KTH/KMH joint programme could be applied within the area of educational tools. Such tools and methods can be used to develop the learning environment within KMH. In *DG1067 Sonology and Studio Technology* at KMH, composition students have the last couple of years been involved in working with experimental music nota-

tion providing data for research in composition and analysis. While their participation was rather as test groups than performing the actual research, the fact that the notation system they used was the subject of current research made them more invested in the work than previous students, who had been provided with a complete and unchanging system (see [16] for more information).

Since 2013 all music production students at KMH are introduced to interactive music production. Students in three courses—*EG1005 Media Production*, *EG1043 Media Production 3*, and *EG1073 Media Production 4*—have been a part of an iterative development process of the interactive music playback framework *iMusic* which is written and maintained by teacher Hans Lindetorp.⁷ Artistic ideas expressed by the students have been the driving factor for new features and the framework and documentation have been tested in projects run by the students.

The Sound Forest [13] is a large-scale Digital Musical Instrument (DMI) situated at the Swedish Museum of Performing Arts. It was designed by researchers from KTH and the experiments on its first prototype were conducted in the framework of a master thesis presented at SMC 2016 [17]. Sound Forest has been used as an experimental platform for several interactive music productions by master students from KMH. The students combine working on their own research questions with participating as informants for research conducted by PhD students at KTH [18].

In the course *EA2001 Music Production 1* during 2014–2016, master students from KMH composed interactive musical soundscapes for the Nobel Price Museum. The exhibition was a multidisciplinary, artistic interpretation of the different prices where students from different artistic schools collaborated to make an interactive installation with audio, video, fashion design, product design, photography and textile design. The project was documented in an article [19].

3.3 Examples of joint course activities

In *DM2350 Human Perception for Information Technology* at KTH, ten students from the jazz department and ten students from the folk-music department at KMH took part in a study on tempo perception in music. The study was planned and conducted by students from the Interactive Media technology master programme at KTH. In addition to results useful in ongoing research, the project also gives students from different school environments an opportunity to create inspiring contact areas for possible later projects. The experimental setting and the measurable results is a new experience for the KMH students, and the KTH students encounter situations and challenges to solve that are hard to replicate in a KTH setting. The experiment is based on identifying the pulse in 20 jazz samples of varying difficulty and identifying the pulse in 20 samples from Swedish folk music by a tapping exercise. These kind of experiments are addressing central themes in Folk Music Theory and the results can also be relevant to course content development at KMH.

⁷ <https://github.com/hanslindetorp/imusic>

In the research on strategies in jazz improvisation, for instance, students from the jazz institution have participated in pilot studies. Apart from the main work that is developing methods, the experiment also helped the students to discover parts of their improvisational ability. They also had the opportunity to reflect on their playing together with a senior teacher. One of the contributing reasons for making the strategies more visible was the technical analysis tools that were being developed and tested within KTH [20].

In the research on the interaction between dancers and musicians in Swedish Folk music students from the folk music department and from the folk dance education at DOCH, School of Dance and Circus at Uniarts participated in Motion Capture pilot studies in the PMIL Performance and Multimodal Interaction Lab at KTH. These experiments relate closely to how these interactions are addressed within the educations and invites students to reflect on research strategies and their own practice.

3.4 Bachelor and Master degree projects

Bachelor and Master's projects at KTH are typically conducted within one semester (15 and 30 ECTS, respectively), with the students making the choice of their thesis subject. Within the SMC team, we provide a list of project topics for the students to choose from, but also encourage them to reshape these or even formulate their own research topic. This process of deciding on the thesis subject is well-supported through the project experiences the students had in previous courses.

In recent years, the outcomes of Master and Bachelor projects are published in a thesis that follows the ACM format with a maximum length of 10 pages. This way, students are prepared and encouraged to use the final thesis as a basis for the submission to a peer-reviewed conference. Before, when the format of the written report was a more traditional one (40 to 100 pages long), the ratio of theses submitted to conferences and the total number of presented theses was usually low. However, we believe that connecting Master theses to ongoing research—both by proposing relevant subjects and by using formats commonly used in research—creates an environment that immediately supports and mutually benefits research and education. Moreover, the conference submissions that actually emerged led to an exposure of the student to a wider community, enabling students to profit from their thesis projects in ways that are relevant for their future employment.

Examples of a master theses that resulted in a peer-reviewed research publication include the work by Emma Frid [21] (best paper award at ICMC - SMC 2014) on the design of tactile display for a live-electronics notification system and that of Lilia Jap [22] who implemented an interactive system for dancers, in which body movements of dancers are tracked in real-time and the playback speed of the audio track is adjusted in interaction with these measurements. In the area of artificial intelligence, another master thesis focused on the analysis of broadcast audio content using deep neural networks, and the work was presented at ISMIR 2019 [23].

Another example was a collaboration between master student Ludvig Elblaus and opera composer and singer Carl Unander-Scharin who was teaching at the University College of Opera. Elblaus' master thesis [24] was awarded best thesis in Sweden in acoustics, published in the SMC conference [25], and invited to Journal of New Music Research [26]. Following this, both Elblaus and Unander-Scharin have completed post-graduate studies at KTH [27, 28].

The Bachelor thesis projects conducted at KTH employ a similar framework as the Master thesis projects. However, the goal of the Bachelor projects is regarded rather as preparation for more elaborate work within a Master thesis, and as a first structured approach to planning, conducting, and presenting research. Despite the limited experience of the Bachelor students, the exposure to a framework that combines research and education has resulted in a number of theses that were presented publicly within conferences and exhibitions [29,30], including accepted submissions to this year's NordicSMC [31,32].

At the heart of the thesis work for music students at KMH is the artistic output. Concerts and scores form essential and necessary parts of their work. But reflective and exploratory work in dialogue with current research has become increasingly important over the past 10 years in the theses. A trend observed among composer students is that of continuing towards a PhD degree after their master. The students themselves decide which aspects of their artistic work they write their theses on. While some describe their creative process in close dialogue with the artistic work, others bring up topics at a more general level though still in relation to their own artistic activities in a form of inside perspective.

The integration of the different approaches to Master thesis work is a challenge in the current collaboration between KMH and KTH, which we approach within the ongoing development of a common framework outlined above. One strategy is the formulation of Master thesis studies at KTH that promote close collaboration with KMH students in their longer projects.

4. DISCUSSION

While it is common that students formulate research questions themselves and design the studies without constraining supervision, an approach where the study is already defined by the teacher has proven to be both efficient and appreciated. Among the reactions in evaluations were that less time was wasted on agreeing on an idea and that they could instead explore a solution space within the framed proposal.

Another finding from course evaluations is that students are in general very positive to be included in ongoing projects and current research as compared to more traditional course work. The tasks become significant, and motivation to study becomes intrinsic. We believe that research in sound and music computing is particularly applicable because most, if not all students, have a personal relationship to the field, it is more intuitive to grasp, and because of its multidisciplinary nature involving different areas such as multimodality,

physical interaction, design, computer science, HCI, perception, and musicology.

With the above illustrated variety of courses with research experience activities included in the intended learning outcomes and course goals, we have as a group built up a strong foundation for undergraduate involvement. Thus, we can in our daily teaching competently offer different opportunities and appropriate challenges for being engaged in research—both in projects with freedom and with more steered tasks.

To conclude, we list the benefits we consider this pedagogical approach will give students in their learning, and faculty in research. These benefits together form our common strategy for including KTH and KMH students in such activities.

4.1 Benefits for students

Students that have partaken in research activities get a first hand experience of how research work can be conducted and therefore a better understanding of what an academic does—something they might then decide to pursue themselves. They learn both to produce results and report these in a format that can lead to publications, that they can add to their portfolio, CV and list of merits for future careers. Naturally, the needs for tutoring the writing process vary depending on a range of factors, but a well-proven and rewarding method for supporting student independence is peer-instruction (among students), which is widely used in our courses.

In terms of the learning outcome, it is known that intrinsic motivation is better for deep learning than grades; it has also been found that a moderate extrinsic motivation enhances the effect of the intrinsic motivation [33,34]. With regards to our course activities, we typically let the examination take the form of an academic report and a project presentation. When students feel they own the project and do a meaningful task, intrinsic motivation increases, and because a published paper gets more visibility than grades, even the extrinsic motivation increases.

4.2 Benefits for research

The group's quantitative research output in the form of peer-reviewed publications cannot be considered to have increased through the involvement of students in research projects. A setting that would aim at this aspect would have senior researchers design experiments and compile the written reports, and students supporting data collection. But, as detailed in the introduction section above, such an approach would be in conflict with various ethical considerations. Instead, we see the major benefit for research in the increased diversity of the research outcomes. Since students are provided the freedom to shape their projects under guidance by experienced researchers, new lines of research are established that go beyond the main research lines of the senior researchers.

4.3 Authorship and ownership

Students and researchers at KTH are protected by policies for intellectual properties (IP). Regulations state that *the basic assumption is that rights to IP created as a result of teaching and research shall vest in the inventor. Inventors can be students as well as employees at KTH.*⁸, and that *if you proposed or own the assignment for the degree project and nothing else was agreed, you own the intellectual property rights that you generate during the assignment.*⁹

In a similar way, the students own the copyrights to all music they create in course-based projects. Therefore it is important to sign agreements on how the music can be used outside the projects, or issue the works with an appropriate licence such as Creative Commons.¹⁰ This involves contracts between students and venues to possibly continue to use the music after a project is finished. It also applies agreements between students and researchers for publishing audio and video resources as references from publications. One positive side effect for the students is that they learn how to handle licences, intellectual property, and contracts as a natural part of their education.

4.4 Strategy

In our dual roles as teachers and researchers, we are aware of the power inequality with regards to students taking our courses and taking part in our ongoing research projects. We intend to continue our tradition of promoting possibilities and providing means for exposure to our academic communities, where students are encouraged to design studies, conduct experiments, and disseminate results.

We need to ensure that course activities are always designed aiming at their intended learning outcomes and supporting incremental development of students' curricula. Researchers should keep within the realm where students can make inspiring learning experiences instead of meeting a closed office door. We must make students aware that their creative and theoretical outputs can substantially contribute to research. In summary we believe that our efforts in engaging students in our research at different stages of their studies have produced very positive results of which both students and researchers are having benefit.

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⁸ Policy for management of intellectual property created at KTH
⁹ <https://www.kth.se/en/samverkan/exjobb/studenter/riktlinjer-1.293804>

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